

PRESIDENTIAL ADDRESS*

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PART I. MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTIONS FOR SCIENTIFIC SUBJECTS

It is well known that the function of a scientific society like ours consists primarily in the exchange of informations and ideas among workers in the same field. This is the way in which science has grown and science can grow. The imposing edifice of science is being built up upon the accumulated knowledge of the past. It is, therefore, necessary that the facts discovered and ideas developed in all lands at all times should be available to all workers in science. The publications of various scientific societies serve mainly as agents for this purpose. An Annual General Meeting of the Society, therefore, offers an occasion on which we can take stock of our achievements and activities in this direction, and discuss the extent to which we have succeeded in exercising this function. A dispassionate analysis of the quality and quantity of papers published in our Journal, however, reveals little justification for complacency or encouragement. Now that India is a free nation, a great responsibility has devolved on us in claiming her rightful position in the scientific world—a sacred task for which we shall have to prepare ourselves so that we may deserve what we aspire after. Looking back to the distant past of India's history, we find that India's contribution in arts, literature, philosophy and science was in no way inferior to that of any of her contemporary nations, if not actually better. It is now an acknowledged fact that India's past achievements in arts, literature and philosophy were of the highest order, and have drawn unstinted admiration and reverence from the best of our modern thinkers. In practical sciences too, I shall refer here only to chemistry in which we are interested, her contributions were far ahead of the time. The famous wrought iron pillar at Delhi near Kutab, believed to have been constructed in the 4th century A.D., which has wonderfully withstood the onslaught of rain and air for over fifteen centuries, numerous iron beams and clamps of very large dimension in the temple of Bhubaneswar and at Konarak (600-900 A.D.), huge iron girders in the temple of Puri (1174 A.D.), the solid copper bolt in the Rampura Asoka pillar near Nepal, believed to be a product of the 3rd century B.C., the huge copper statue of Buddha weighing about 1 ton found at Sultangunge in Bhagalpur and believed to be a product of the 5th century A.D., are but a few of the numerous evidences of the remarkable skill displayed by the early Indians in large scale metallurgical and metal work, inspite of poor appliances at their disposal at the time. In the field of preparative chemistry reference may be made to the preparation of *mridu kshara* or mild

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alkali (carbonate) and *tikshna kshara* or caustic alkali so meticulously described in the Ayurvedic treatise *Susruta* as early as the 5th century B.C. These methods are characterized by such a high degree of perfection that they can be bodily transferred to any modern text-book of chemistry. While recalling these glorious achievements of our forefathers in distant ages we cannot overlook the fact that as soon as India lost her freedom she practically sank into a dark age with absolutely no record worthy of note regarding her activities in experimental sciences, and, as the late Sir P. C. Ray very painfully but appropriately puts, "her name was all but expunged from the map of the scientific world". From this intellectual torpor there has, however, been an awakening from the beginning of the present century, and while India regains her freedom to-day it becomes a bounden duty for every one of us to put forth his best to revive her ancient glory, so that we may claim for her once again a rightful position in the scientific world and prove ourselves worthy of our great cultural heritage.

I cannot but refer here to a matter with which we, as scientists, are vitally interested, and with which the scientific progress and welfare of the country are intimately associated. You are all aware that with the dawn of freedom in our country there has been a popular demand for changing the medium of instructions in our universities from English into the language of our own country, and the Governments of many provinces have already adopted the provincial vernacular as their Court language. This is quite natural and is as it should be from the nationalistic point of view. But fortunately or unfortunately in India many things, which are quite natural and obvious in other countries, assume a somewhat different and complicated aspect from the viewpoint of her national growth and national welfare, because of her unusual geographical position, her colourful past history, variety of her provincial languages, and diversity of her population and their habits of life. That instruction in a foreign language in schools, colleges, and universities is not only absurd and unnatural, but positively detrimental to understanding and progress, involving an unnecessary and huge waste of time and energy, needs no discussion. But the question is what should be the medium of instruction in different provinces of India. If each province adheres to its own provincial language as it naturally does even up to a certain standard now, a considerable difficulty would be experienced in inter-provincial cultural intercourse and administrative activities. Migration of students from one provincial university to another, selection of teachers from one province for another, recruitment of officers and specialists for central public services will be associated with enormous difficulties, if not altogether inoperative and unpracticable. If a national *lingua franca* for the entire Indian dominion be adopted, as is suggested, which may be Hindi or Hindusthani, then, in addition to each provincial language, the national language should also be made compulsory for every stage of our education. Besides, if we are to keep ourselves in touch with the cultural flow of Europe and America, we shall have to retain English as a compulsory second language in all our colleges and universities; otherwise, we would isolate and cripple ourselves both intellectually and culturally. All these difficulties are sure to multiply manifold in the case of scientific subjects with their characteristic terminologies and symbols. Imagine the way in which we shall have to carry out our discussion in all-India

scientific gatherings like Indian Science Congress Sessions, the National Institute of Sciences of India, and the various All-India Scientific Societies like ours. What will be the character of our organ, the Journal of the Indian Chemical Society, and, for the matter of that, of all other similar scientific journals now published in India? If workers of different provinces send in their contributions in their own provincial languages and scripts, it will create not only serious difficulties in their printing and publication, but will defeat the very purpose of such journals, which, as has been stated above, aims at a free and unfettered exchange of informations and ideas for the progress of science. It may, however, be argued that the publications will be made only in the *lingua franca* of India and in a script of its own with common terminologies. Then again, it has to be considered whether under such altered conditions we shall be able to maintain our exchange relation with the learned societies of Europe and America undisturbed, and whether our publications will receive due notice in the Abstracts of foreign countries, which is so essential to our activities and progress. I am afraid, it will be too much to expect such recognition from abroad unless our contributions attain such a high standard as to compel the foreign scientists to look for light and guidance from us. We shall thus be cut off and isolated from the scientific progress of the world, which we certainly do not desire.

I have rather dwelt at some length on this problem as I consider it to be of fundamental importance to our national welfare, our scientific progress and social advancement. The problem, as I have shown, cannot be solved province-wise. It is an all-India problem and should be thoroughly discussed in All-India Organizations. First of all, the various All-India Scientific Societies should discuss this problem in their individual organizations and communicate their considered opinions to the Indian Science Congress Association and the National Institute of Sciences of India. The representatives of these two bodies, after the matter has been discussed in their respective organizations with due consideration of the opinions of the All-India Scientific Societies, should then meet together along with one representative each of these Scientific Societies for a final recommendation on the subject to the Government of the Union. All attempts to provincialize the scientific terminologies and symbols should be discouraged. That will lead only to disintegration and confusion, while science aims at integration. What is required is a dispassionate consideration of the problem free from sentiment, pride and prejudices.

PART II. STEREOCHEMISTRY OF NICKEL, COPPER AND SILVER

I shall now proceed to the scientific portion of my address as I do not like to be guilty of the violation of a wholesome convention for the President of your Society. I have, therefore, chosen to speak to-day on the stereochemistry of nickel, copper and silver in which I have been interested for some time.

From a consideration of the physical and chemical properties of the co-ordination compounds chemists distinguished them long ago into two classes; *viz.*, perfect or

strong, and imperfect or weak complexes. Those, which are unstable or dissociate readily in aqueous solution, are regarded as weak or imperfect complexes, and the stable ones, whose dissociation in aqueous solution is negligible, are placed in the group of strong or perfect complexes. As no sharp line of demarcation could be drawn between these properties, they assumed that the two classes merge insensibly into each other, and the transition between them is a *continuous* one. As an illustration, we may cite here a number of complex nickel compounds, such as potassium nickelocyanide, $K_2[Ni(CN)_4]$, nickel dimethyl glyoxime,

nickel ethylenediamine thiocyanate, $\left[Ni \left(\begin{array}{c} CH_2-NH_2 \\ | \\ CH_2-NH_2 \end{array} \right)_2 \right] (SCN)_2$, nickel tetrammine

sulphate, $[Ni(NH_3)_4]SO_4$, etc. The first two substances, potassium nickelocyanide and nickel dimethylglyoxime, belong to the group of perfect complexes, as they are not attacked by the usual reagents for nickel, like caustic alkali, sulphuretted hydrogen, etc. The last two, nickel ethylenediamine thiocyanate and nickel tetrammine sulphate, give at once a precipitate of nickel sulphide on treatment with hydrogen sulphide; they also give a precipitate of nickel hydroxide with caustic alkali. These substances should, therefore, be viewed as imperfect complexes. A determination of the concentration of free nickel ions in their equivalent solutions lends further support to this view. This naturally raises the question about the nature of the bond in co-ordination complexes. With the development of the electronic theory of valency two different views were advanced in order to elucidate this point. Kossel (*Ann. Physik*, 1916, **49**, 229), in accordance with his theory of chemical combination as due to electrostatic attraction between oppositely charged particles, suggested that in the formation of co-ordination compounds also a similar electrostatic attraction should play the main role. Hence the bonds between the central atom and the co-ordinated units are of the polar type, or ionic in character. On the other hand, Lewis (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, **38**, 762), Langmuir (*ibid.*, 1919, **41**, 868) and Sidgwick (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **123**, 725) hold that the bonds in the co-ordination complexes are of the non-polar or covalent type, due to the sharing of a pair of electrons per bond, donated by the co-ordinated units to the central atom. Neither of these views can obviously account for the properties of all types of complexes. That in some of the complexes the bonds are predominantly of the non-polar type was more or less definitely established by the classical work of Werner on co-ordination complexes, leading to the isolation of isomeric and optically active compounds. A deter-

mination of the magnetic properties of a large variety of complex compounds led the present speaker (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, 174, 191) to classify the co-ordination complexes into two distinct types, polar and non-polar, the transition between which must be a *discontinuous* one. In the polar class the bonds are believed to be ionic, and in the non-polar they are supposed to be covalent. Referring to the series of nickel complexes cited above, potassium nickelocyanide and nickel dimethylglyoxime were found to be diamagnetic, while the other two showed paramagnetism, practically identical with that for nickelous ion. In order to account for the striking change of magnetic properties in many of these non-polar co-ordination compounds, it was suggested that such changes were usually associated with the more or less complete filling up of the $3d$ -orbital of the central atom with electrons in the case of the elements of the first transitional group. In other words, in those cases where the electrons supplied by the co-ordinated units during the bond formation enter the inner d -level of the central atom, leading thereby to a coupling of the unbalanced electrons originally present in the atom, a profound alteration in the paramagnetic properties of the atom will result. The two types of complexes were, therefore, termed *penetration* and *associated* complexes. In the latter, it is regarded that the bonds are either ionic, or the electrons of the co-ordination bonds avoid entering the inner d -level. This is in fairly good agreement with the view developed by Pauling on the basis of quantum mechanics in his well-known and comprehensive theory of co-ordination compounds, which relates the nature of the bond orbitals with the spatial configuration of the molecules, and has thus provided a theoretical basis for stereochemistry (Pauling, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 53, 1367; cf. also "The Nature of the Chemical Bond", 1940). According to this view, hybrid bond orbitals formed by the linear combination of s - and p -orbitals of the valency shell with one or two d -orbitals of the penultimate valence shell are of special significance in accounting for the configuration of the co-ordination compounds of the penetration type. Four strong equivalent hybrid $d:sp^2$ bond orbitals lead to a planar square configuration of the four-coordinated complexes; similarly six strong equivalent hybrid $d^2:sp^3$ bond orbitals give rise to a regular octahedral configuration of the co-ordinated units around the central atom. This, in fact, provides a theoretical justification of Werner's theory regarding the configuration of complex compounds, which was placed on a solid foundation by his own classical work. On the other hand, four equivalent hybrid sp^3 bond orbitals or sp^2d bond orbitals, formed with orbitals of the same valency shell, have been shown by Pauling to give rise to a tetrahedral and planar square configuration respectively for four-coordinated complexes of the associated type. The octahedral complexes of the associated type similarly result from the use of six equivalent hybrid sp^3d^2 bond orbitals, derived from the same valence shell. The bonds in these associated complexes, as their electronic configurations show, may resonate between the covalent and the ionic type. A consideration of the electronic configurations of the nickel, copper and silver complexes makes it clear, and enables us directly to deduce the magnetic moment of their central atoms on the basis of Bose-Stoner's formula:

$$\mu_n = \sqrt{4S(S+1)} ;$$

where S = the resultant spin moment. Conversely, a knowledge of the magnetic moment

of a co-ordination complex can, in many cases, reveal the nature of the bond involved in its formation and disclose the structure of the molecule itself.

Electrons in Ions and Co-ordination Complexes.

	3d	4s	4p	4d	μ_B (obsv.)
Ni ²⁺	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\uparrow$				2.8—3.2
Do-Complex Fourfold— sp^3 or sp^3d	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\uparrow$	$\uparrow\downarrow$	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow$		2.8—3.0
Do— dsp^2	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow$	$\uparrow\downarrow$	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow$		Dia.
Do-Complex Sixfold— d^2sp^3	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow$	$\uparrow\downarrow$	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow$	$\uparrow\uparrow$	3.0
Ni ²⁺	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\uparrow\uparrow\uparrow$				(4.9) theor.
Do-Complex sixfold— d^2sp^3	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow$	$\uparrow\downarrow$	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow$		Dia.
Cu ²⁺	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\uparrow$				μ_B (obsv.) 1.95—2.0
Do-Complex Sixfold— sp^3d^2	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\uparrow$	$\uparrow\downarrow$	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow$	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow$	1.84
Do-Complex Fourfold— sp^3 or sp^3d	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\uparrow$	$\uparrow\downarrow$	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow$		1.86-1.94
Do— dsp^2	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow$	$\uparrow\downarrow$	$\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow\downarrow\uparrow$		1.73-1.84

The octahedral configuration for the six-covalent co-ordination complexes of many transitional elements was suggested and proved by Werner from a consideration of their chemical and electrochemical behaviour, as well as by the isolation of isomers and the resolution of asymmetric bodies into optically active components. The determination of the crystal structure by the X-ray method in recent times of some compounds, containing octahedral complexes, provides the most direct confirmation of Werner's view in this respect.

In the case of four-covalent complexes, Werner as long ago as 1893 suggested co-planar configuration for bivalent palladium or platinum atoms in certain molecules, in order to account for the isomerism of compounds like $\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_2\text{Cl}_2$. The planar configuration for $[\text{PdCl}_4]^{2-}$ and $[\text{PtCl}_4]^{2-}$ ions in K_2PdCl_4 and K_2PtCl_4 has been subsequently established by the X-ray method. There was no definite evidence for planar configuration for 4-covalent complexes formed by elements like nickel, copper or silver, till Pauling developed his theory of complex compounds in 1931, as discussed above. It has now been shown that many diamagnetic complexes of bivalent nickel exist in two isomeric forms. These include nickel dimethylglyoxime (Tschugaeff, *J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 42, 1466), nickel benzylmethylglyoxime (Sugden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 246), bithiosemicarbazide nickelous sulphate (Jensen, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1936, 229, 265), which are readily interconvertible. The co-planar structure of nickel dithio-oxalate ion and nickel salicyaldoxime has been established by the X-ray method (cf. Cox, Wardlaw and Webster, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 459, 1475). Nickel phthalocyanine furnishes another instance of the kind (Robertson, *ibid.*, 1935, 615). Three different modifications of nickel phenylbiguanide also were isolated in our laboratory (Ray and

Chakrabarty, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 614). These differ in their colour, solubility and decomposition temperature, and are distinguished as α -, β - and γ - forms. The α -base is brick-red in colour, insoluble in water, but soluble in alcohol and acetone, changing rapidly into the yellow γ -variety. The same change occurs on keeping it in contact, or on heating, with water. It decomposes at 255° . The β -base is light yellow in colour, insoluble in water and all common organic solvents. On heating, it decomposes at 265° . The γ -form is deep yellow in colour, also insoluble in water and all organic solvents. It decomposes at 263° . From a consideration of the constitution of nickel phenylbiguanide it may be suggested that these possibly represent some of the various forms in which a molecule of this type is likely to occur, provided, of course, we do not attribute this difference in properties solely to polymorphism, for which, however, there is little justification. The α - and β -varieties were regarded as *cis*- and *trans*-isomer respectively as shown below :

The *cis*-modification may again exist in two different forms; in one, both the phenyl groups would lie on the same side of the plane, while in the other, it would occur on the opposite sides. The latter, having no plane of symmetry, might again occur in two optically active forms.

A very interesting case of isomerism has been described by Lifschitz and co-workers (*Z. anorg. allg. Chem.*, 1939, 242, 97). This relates to the fourfold nickel complexes of stilbenediamine and monophenylethylenediamine. Each member of these two series of nickel complexes has been obtained in two different forms, yellow and blue. The former are diamagnetic, and the latter, paramagnetic like the simple nickel salts. They, therefore, represent respectively complexes of the penetration type, having square planar configuration with dsp^2 bonds, and of the associated type with tetrahedral sp^3 or square sp^3d bonds, resonating with ionic bonds. A glance at the electronic configuration of nickel complexes, given above, makes it clear. It is further significant to note that all diamagnetic fourfold nickel complexes, which belong to the penetration type, are yellow, orange, or red in colour; while all paramagnetic fourfold complexes, which are of the associated type, are blue or green in colour. This seems to suggest a relationship between the colour of the complex and the type of its structure and bond.

Octahedral bivalent nickel complexes with d^2sp^3 bonds should show a moment value due to two unpaired electrons promoted to the $4d$ -level. This is illustrated by the magnetic moment of nickel *tris*dipyridyl salts (Ray and Sen, unpublished).

On the other hand, a sixfold quadrivalent nickel, as in barium or ammonium nickel molybdate, has been found to be diamagnetic, and hence it forms six octahedral d^2sp^3 bonds. The composition of these complexes is rather unusual and is given by the formula, $3(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{O}(\text{BaO})\cdot\text{NiO}_2\cdot 9\text{MoO}_3\cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$. It is, therefore, suggested that they should be regarded as molecular compounds of 6-molybdenum and 12-molybdenum heteropolyacid salts, viz., $\text{R}_{11}\text{H}_4[\text{Ni}^{\text{IV}}(\text{MoO}_4)_6]\cdot\text{R}_6[\text{Ni}^{\text{IV}}(\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7)_6]$, or better as $\text{R}_2\text{H}_2[\text{Ni}^{\text{IV}}(\text{MoO}_4)_3\cdot(\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7)_3]$, a new type of 9-molybdenum heteropoly complex salt (Ray *et al.*, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 25 51). Alkali nickel periodates, $\text{K}(\text{Na})\text{NiIO}_6$, with tetrapositive nickel, recently prepared in our laboratory (Ray and Sarma, *Nature*, 1946, 627), have been found to give a very low magnetic moment value, about 1 Bohr magneton, which is even lower than that required for the presence of one unpaired electron. But, as is evident from the scheme of electronic configuration shown above, a quadrivalent nickel ion would have given a much higher moment value, about 5 Bohr magnetons. It is, therefore, concluded that the quadrivalent nickel atom is present in the crystal as the centre of a co-ordination complex and is surrounded octahedrally by six oxygen atoms, the bonds between the nickel and the oxygen atoms being predominantly covalent of the d^2sp^3 type. The compound in its crystalline state thus behaves as a penetration complex, though the molecular composition corresponds to a mixed alkali nickel salt of orthoperiodic acid.

Similar autocomplex formation in the solid state has been observed also in the case of some simple bivalent nickel compounds. Anhydrous nickel cyanide, for instance, gives a moment value of only $0.65 \mu_B$ (Ray and Sabu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 161). It has, therefore, been suggested that the nickel atom in the crystal forms a planar square complex with the surrounding CN-groups by means of dsp^2 bonds, giving rise to a chain polymer as depicted below :

or $\text{Ni} [\text{Ni}_4(\text{CN})_{16}]$.

There are some sixfold copper complexes with the metal atom in the bivalent state. These may be regarded as belonging to the associated class either with octahedral sp^3d^2 bonds or ion-dipole bonds, or with bonds resonating between these two. Bivalent copper is not likely to form octahedral penetration complexes with their characteristic d^2sp^3 bonds, as there are not sufficient d -orbitals of the inner shell available for bond formation. For, this would require promotion of three electrons to a higher level, involving a considerable expenditure of energy. The configuration, therefore, indicates that the magnetic moment of these complexes remain practically unaltered from that of the simple cupric ion. This has been verified in the case of copper *tris*ethylenediamine and *tris*pyridine complexes, as well as for $\text{K}_2\text{Ca}[\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_2)_6]$ and similar salts (Ray and Sabu, *loc. cit.*).

Bivalent copper like bivalent nickel is very prone to form fourfold complexes. All the fourfold copper complexes, that have been examined by the X-ray method, show a planar structure. These include compounds like $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{K}_2\text{CuCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{Py}$, copper acetylacetonate, copper phthalocyanine, copper salicylaldoxime, copper picolinate, etc. The isomorphism of copper methylethylglyoxime with the corresponding nickel compound is also an evidence for the planar structure of the former. We have already seen that in the case of fourfold nickel complexes, measurement of magnetic moments provided a very convenient and convincing method for distinguishing the complexes of the penetration type from those of the associated class, as the former are all diamagnetic and the latter give the same paramagnetic moment as the simple nickel salts. This, however, is not possible in the case of fourfold copper complexes. As their electronic configurations show that in both types of complexes there would remain one unpaired electron in the central metal atom as in a simple cupric ion. This will lead almost to the same moment value for all. Nevertheless, a small but measurable difference in the moment value for the two types of complexes might be expected in view of the difference in the position of the unpaired electron in the two cases. An examination of their electronic configurations would show that in the penetration complexes the unpaired electron occupies a higher level, $4p$; while it occurs as a $3d$ -electron in the associated type as well as in simple cupric ion. Pauling ("The Nature of the Chemical Bond", 1940, p. 121), in fact, suggested that the planar complexes should show a lower moment value than the tetrahedral ones, because of the greater quenching effect of the more unsymmetrical field of the attached groups upon the residual orbital moment of the electron. For, the moment of the cupric ion in solution is always higher than the theoretical value of $1.73\mu_B$ on the basis of Bose-Stoner's formula, indicating the presence of a residual orbital moment. But no evidence of a tetrahedral cupric complex has yet been obtained by the X-ray method. All the compounds examined show planar structure; consequently, the bonds involved are either of dsp^2 or sp^2d type, corresponding to the penetration and associated complexes respectively. Hence, if there be any lower moment value for the 4-covalent copper complexes of the penetration type, it would be more likely due to the fact that in these the lone electron being promoted to a higher level is less influenced by the nuclear field with the consequent increase in the perturbing and quenching effect of the field of the neighbouring atoms and ions on its orbital moment. A systematic and careful measurement of a large variety of fourfold cupric complexes in our laboratory seems to provide a method for dividing these complexes into two such groups. It has been found that the moment value for one group, particularly after θ -correction, lies near about $1.73\mu_B$, while that of the other group is very nearly equal to $2\mu_B$. The former, therefore, represents the complexes of the penetration type and the latter, those of the associated one.

It is, however, of some significance to note in this connection that all those 4-covalent bivalent copper complexes, which show a lower moment value of about 1.73 - $1.84\mu_B$, are either red, dark brown, greenish yellow, or deep blue in colour, while those, giving a higher moment value of 1.9 - $2.2\mu_B$, are all green, blue, or blue-violet in colour. To a certain extent a distinction can thus be made between the penetration and the associated complexes of bivalent copper merely from their colour.

Notwithstanding their planar configuration, there is little definite evidence of geometrical isomerism among the 4-covalent copper complexes. Pfeiffer and Glaser (*J. prakt. Chem.*, 1939, ii, 153, 265) have described two modifications of naphthaldehyde methylimine copper, one forming dark brown needles of metallic lustre and the other consisting of green needles, the latter changing into the brown variety at 140° or on keeping under methyl alcohol at the room temperature. But both gave solutions of identical colour in pyridine. Pfeiffer and Krebs (*ibid.*, 1939, 155, 77) have also isolated two forms of sodium and barium salts of copper salicylaldehyde phenylimine *p*-sulphonic acid, which differ in their solubility in solvents like glycol or glycerine. Whether the difference in these cases is due to dimorphism or *cis-trans* isomerism could not be decided by the authors. Two modifications of copper phenylbiguanide salts have also been prepared by us. The chloride, for instance, has been obtained in bluish violet as well as in brick-red crystals, the former changing into the latter at 101° in presence of steam, or in long contact with water. They differ in their melting point, solubility and rate of hydrolysis, but give identical absorption spectra in aqueous solution (Ray and Chakrabarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 609). Recently, we have obtained two modifications of copper bisdiethylbiguanide, which differ markedly in their colour. One forms deep blue crystals and the other forms bright red needles (m.p. 199°), the latter changing into the blue variety in long contact with water, while the former changes into the latter at 160°. They are insoluble in water, but dissolve readily in alcohol and other organic solvents. In solution they give identical absorption spectra. As they both give almost the same but a low magnetic moment value of 1.98 μ_B only, they are both 4-covalent complexes of the penetration type. In view of their great difference in colour we are disposed to think that they do really represent a case of geometrical isomerism and are related as *cis-trans* isomers to each other.

A simple salt, *viz.* anhydrous cupric chloride, CuCl₂, unlike its hydrated variety, also has been found to give a lower moment value of 1.73 μ_B and hence behaves like a 4-covalent penetration complex with *dsp*² bonds. Like anhydrous nickel cyanide and palladous chloride, it can, therefore, be represented as an endless, long-chained, polymeric molecule.

Some copper complexes with copper in the tervalent state, namely alkali copper periodate and tellurate, have been described by Malatesta (*Gazzetta*, 1941, 71, 467, 580). They are diamagnetic and their composition is represented by the formula, M₇Cu(IO₆)₂·xH₂O and M₃Cu(TeO₆)₂·nH₂O respectively. Their diamagnetic character can only result from an electronic configuration corresponding to that for a 4-covalent penetration complex of bivalent nickel, as shown in the scheme above. Each copper atom in the molecule, therefore, forms four co-planar *dsp*² bonds with four oxygen atoms of two (IO₆)⁵⁻ or (TeO₆)⁶⁻ groups, as can be represented by the formula,

for the periodate.

Now dealing with the stereochemistry of the remaining element, bivalent silver like bivalent copper has been found to form 4-covalent planar complexes of the penetra-

tion type. They show the same moment value as the corresponding copper complexes, viz., $1.73 \mu_B$, appropriate to one unpaired electron. This is clear from their electronic configuration. Planar configuration for the bivalent silver picolinate has been verified by the X-ray method and by isomorphism with the corresponding cupric compound (Cox, *et. al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 775).

Recently we have prepared in our laboratory a number of complex trivalent silver salts of ethylenedibiguanide with fourfold co-ordination (Ray and Chakrabarty, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21 47). They are diamagnetic and hence presumably possess an electronic configuration similar to that for a planar bivalent nickel complex of the penetration type, since a tripositive silver ion resembles the bivalent nickel ion in its configuration. Consequently, silver in its trivalent state forms co-planar bonds of the dsp^2 type in its fourfold complexes. The trivalent silver periodates and tellurates, described by Malatesta (*loc. cit.*), which are also diamagnetic like the corresponding copper compounds, should, therefore, be represented like these latter as 4-covalent complexes of the penetration type with a planar structure.

This concludes a brief review of the stereochemistry of the three common coinage metals; and it is really interesting to note that the modern and more refined physical methods have confirmed and placed on a sounder basis the views previously deduced by the classical methods of chemistry.